

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XLVI. Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium-, Mercury(II) with ON-x-NO Donor Doubly-bidentate Chelating Schiff Bases

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Schiff bases derived from 4,4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone with salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde behave as ON-x-NO donor doubly-bidentate ligands and form dinuclear complexes with divalent Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg ions. The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are found to be either octahedral or distorted-octahedral, whereas a tetrahedral stereochemistry can be assigned to the Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes. The complexes have been characterised by analytical, conductance, magnetic, ir, electronic, esr and nmr spectral data.

Sulphones are reported¹ to possess strong therapeutic properties. In continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis and characterisation of polymetallic complexes containing multidentate ligands, we report here the preparation of two new Schiff bases and their Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are amorphous in nature, having high melting point and are insoluble in common organic solvents but feebly soluble in dimethylformamide and dioxane. Non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated from low Λ_M values in DMF (4.2–6.8 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$). The complexes have the compositions $[\text{M}_2\text{L}_2/\text{L}'_2 (\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ and $[\text{ML}_2/\text{L}'_2]$, where $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}, \text{M}' = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}, \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}$, $\text{LH}_2 = 4,4'$ -di-(salicylidene)diphenylsulphone; $\text{L}'\text{H}_2 = 4,4'$ -di-(naphthalidene)diphenylsulphone.

The ligands revealed sharp ir bands at 1605 (LH_2) and 1600 cm^{-1} ($\text{L}'\text{H}_2$) due to azomethine linkage. In all the metal complexes this band appears at a higher frequency region, indicating the involvement of azomethine nitrogen atom to the metal ions². The broad ligand band at 2850–2950 cm^{-1} (intramolecular O–H...N hydrogen bonding) disappeared in the metal chelates, suggesting

the deprotonation of phenolic OH groups. The band at 1260 (LH_2) and 1270 cm^{-1} ($\text{L}'\text{H}_2$) can be assigned to the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ vibration. In the metal complexes this band shifted down to lower frequency region by about 10 cm^{-1} showing the bonding of both the phenolic oxygen atoms to the metal ions³. The bands at 1150–1155 and 1320–1380 cm^{-1} in the ligands and the complexes can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{as}} (\text{O}=\text{S}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}} (\text{O}=\text{S}=\text{O})$ vibrations respectively. The presence of coordinated water molecules in the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes is indicated by the appearance of sharp bands and double humps at about 3450 cm^{-1} followed by a sharp peak at about 850 cm^{-1} attributable to stretching and rocking vibrations respectively⁴. In all the complexes medium to weak bands were observed at 500–510 and 340–355 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ respectively⁵.

The electronic spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes exhibited ligand field bands at about 8955, 18125, 20800 and 32500 cm^{-1} . The first three bands can be attributed to ${}^4\text{T}_{1\text{g}} (\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2\text{g}} (\text{F}) (\nu_1) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2\text{g}} (\text{F}) (\nu_2)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1\text{g}} (\text{P}) (\nu_3)$ transitions, whereas the fourth band is a CT band. The ligand field parameters like Dq (917.0, 877.5 cm^{-1}), B (809.3, 795.1 cm^{-1}), ν_2/ν_1 (2.02, 2.0), β_{35} (0.83, 0.81) and σ (20.48, 23.45) suggest an octahedral stereochemistry. In

the electronic spectra of the copper(II) complexes, one broad asymmetric band appeared at 13 450–14 875 cm^{-1} with maxima at 14 250 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition. Both Jahn-Teller distortion and mixed N,O donor atoms contribute to the broadening of the absorption band, suggestive of distorted-octahedral geometry for the copper(II) complexes. For both the nickel complexes, the bands observed at about 11 270, 18 360, 26 540 and 35 400 cm^{-1} may be assigned respectively to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2), $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions and CT band. The values of spectral parameters like Dq (1127, 115 cm^{-1}), B (739.3, 737.6 cm^{-1}), β_{35} (0.71, 0.70), ν_2/ν_1 (1.62, 1.63) and σ (40.84, 42.85) support an octahedral stereochemistry around the metal ions⁸.

Sub-normal magnetic moments of the complexes of Co^{II} (2.7, 2.6), Ni^{II} (2.84, 2.52) and Cu^{II} (1.30, 1.35 B.M.) indicate metal-metal interaction in a polymeric structure. It can be assigned to the fact that the unpaired electron of the d -orbital of the metal ion may overlap with the π -orbital of the nitrogen atom of the azomethine (C=N) group of the ligands. Due to the high electron density of the N-atoms, it is but possible for an electron from nitrogen to move to partially occupy the d -orbital of the metal ion with antiparallel spin to that of the original d -electron. As a result, the magnetic moments are aligned antiparallel and being responsible for partial quenching of paramagnetism due to super-exchange phenomenon.

The molecular weight data of the complexes are in agreement with dimeric structures of the complexes.

The TGA study of the complex $[\text{Cu}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ shows that the compound is stable upto 180°. Thereafter it registers a mass-loss of 23.2% at 180–220° against the theoretical value of 22.54% which corresponds to the loss of four water molecules and 1/5th of the ligand moiety. Thereafter the complex suffers a mass-loss of 27.84% at 260–340° and 18.5% at 340–400°. After 400° the thermogram becomes almost a straight line and at 400–1000° loses 18.28%. The total mass-loss is 87.88% which shows the formation of CuO .

The esr spectra of the complexes $[\text{Cu}_2\text{L}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ and $[\text{Cu}_2\text{L}'_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ were recorded at X-band. In case of the latter complex the g_{av} value was found to be 2.0678 by using Kneubuhl's method¹⁰. The esr spectrum is found to be isotropic consisting of a single line characteristic of regular geometry. This type of spectrum may result either due to pseudo-rotational type of Jahn-Teller distortion or due to the extensive exchange coupling operating between the Cu^{II} ions in a dinuclear structure¹¹. The esr spectrum of the former complex at X-band showed that the geometry around Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell is tetragonal (elongated octahedral) with $g_{\perp} = 2.0578$ and $g_{\parallel} = 2.1618$. The axial symmetry parameter (G) comes out to be 2.79 indicating strong exchange interaction among the magnetically equivalent Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell¹².

${}^1\text{H}$ nmr spectra of the ligands LH_2 and $\text{L}'\text{H}_2$ showed peaks at δ 8.3–8.5 (azomethine protons). The signals at δ 5.6 and 5.5 observed in the ligands LH_2 and $\text{L}'\text{H}_2$ are due to Ar-OH hydroxy protons. The complex pattern shown at δ 6.5–8.1 (LH_2) and 6.7–8.2 ($\text{L}'\text{H}_2$) is due to sixteen and twenty phenyl protons respectively.

The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are tetrahedral in configuration basing upon analytical and ir spectral data.

Both the Schiff bases behave as doubly-bidentate chelating ligands and coordinate to the metal ions through both the phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms favouring the formation of a dinuclear structure :

where, $M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}, \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$, $y = \text{H}_2\text{O}$; $M = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}, \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}, \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}$, $y = \text{nil}$

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. An

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. wt. found	VC=N/ VC-O	VM-O/ VM-N
	M	C	H	N			
LH ₂ (Yellow)	—	67.7 (68.42)	4.1 (4.38)	5.8 (6.14)	425	1 605 1 260	—
L'H ₂ (Brick red)	—	72.5 (73.38)	4.2 (4.31)	4.7 (5.03)	515	1 600 1 270	—
[Co ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (Pink)	10.6 (10.73)	56.4 (56.84)	3.8 (4.00)	4.9 (5.10)	1 012	1 620 1 250	500 355
[Co ₂ L' ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (Red)	8.6 (9.07)	62.4 (62.87)	3.8 (4.00)	4.2 (4.31)	1 235	1 615 1 260	505 350
[Ni ₂ L' ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (Green)	10.4 (10.69)	56.2 (56.86)	3.8 (4.00)	4.8 (5.10)	1 020	1 615 1 250	510 350
[Ni ₂ L' ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (Brown)	8.8 (9.04)	62.5 (62.89)	3.9 (4.00)	4.1 (4.31)	1 190	1 610 1 255	500 340
[Cu ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (Greenish yellow)	11.2 (11.47)	56.1 (56.36)	3.8 (3.97)	4.8 (5.05)	1 030	1 620 1 255	505 345
[Cu ₂ L' ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] (Grey)	9.5 (9.71)	62.2 (62.43)	3.8 (3.97)	4.1 (4.28)	1 210	1 615 1 260	510 350
[Zn ₂ L ₂] (White)	12.3 (12.58)	59.5 (60.07)	3.2 (3.46)	5.1 (5.39)	945	1 615 1 250	510 340
[Zn ₂ L' ₂] (Yellow)	10.3 (10.55)	65.2 (65.87)	3.4 (3.55)	4.3 (4.52)	1 115	1 615 1 260	505 345
[Cd ₂ L ₂] (White)	19.6 (19.84)	54.6 (55.08)	2.9 (3.17)	4.8 (4.94)	1 050	1 620 1 245	500 350
[Cd ₂ L' ₂] (Red)	16.6 (16.86)	60.7 (61.22)	3.2 (3.30)	3.9 (4.20)	1 265	1 615 1 255	500 355
[Hg ₂ L ₂] l(Yellow)	30.4 (30.63)	47.2 (47.66)	2.6 (2.75)	4.1 (4.27)	1 230	1 615 1 250	510 350
[Hg ₂ L' ₂] (Pale red)	26.2 (26.57)	53.5 (54.07)	2.8 (2.91)	3.6 (3.71)	1 375	1 620 1 260	500 345

ethanolic solution of 4,4'-diaminodiphenyl sulphone (2.48 g) was mixed separately with salicylaldehyde (2.44 ml) and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (3.44 g) in presence of piperidine (5–6 drops) in the ratio of 1 : 2 and the mixture refluxed for ~ 2 h over a water-bath. On cooling, yellow Schiff bases separated out. These were washed with ethanol, dried on exposure to air and crystallised from ethanol (95%).

Preparation of the complexes : The Schiff bases in ethanol were mixed separately with ethanolic solutions of the metal chlorides in 1 : 1 molar ratios. The mixture was warmed for about 0.5 h over a water-bath. After cooling, pH of the solution was raised to ~ 7 by adding concentrated ammonia when metal chelates separated out. These were washed with ethanol, dried under reduced pressure.

Metal, C, N and H were determined by standard methods. Conductances were measured in 10⁻³

M acetone. Magnetic susceptibility measurements of solid samples were made by the Gouy method. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (in 10⁻² *M* acetone solution of the complexes) on a Hilger and Watt UVispeck spectrophotometer, esr spectra on a E-4 spectrometer at room temperature and nmr spectra on a EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer. The molecular weight was determined by Rast method using camphor as solid solvent.

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